

CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO ADULT LEARNERS

Rakhimova Zulfizar Sukhrobovna

Teacher of English at the chair of “Innovation educational technologies and pedagogy” of
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10160010>

Abstract. *This scholarly article delves into the distinctive features of instructing foreign languages to adult learners. It highlights the essential pedagogical requisites conducive to efficacious foreign language acquisition by adults and scrutinizes the multifaceted dimensions of this subject.*

Keywords: *foreign language, adult learners, linguistic proficiency, motivation, pedagogical requisites, competence-oriented approach*

In the contemporary landscape of a globalized society, marked by the expansion of international interactions and collaboration across political, economic, and cultural domains, there exists a burgeoning demand among adults to acquire proficiency in a foreign language. This requisite is fundamental for their active engagement in international business and cultural exchange. Nevertheless, many adults grapple with certain challenges in the process of acquiring a foreign language. Thus, it becomes imperative to comprehend and accommodate the specific nuances associated with instructing foreign languages to adult learners in order to optimize the educational experience and harness methodological approaches to their fullest potential.

Psychological research reveals a conundrum where, with age, logical memory tends to improve, while short-term memory experiences a decline. Nonetheless, an advantageous corollary of this phenomenon is the interdependence and harmonization of cognitive functions, serving to offset the limitations of individual memory functions [1]. For instance, the wealth of life experiences and the cultivation of logical reasoning abilities may serve as counterweights to constraints in short-term memory. Moreover, the role of linguistic proficiency emerges as a pivotal factor that can exert both constructive and detrimental influences on the efficacy of the learning process. Insufficiencies in the comprehension of one's native language may impede the acquisition of grammatical and lexical structures, thereby complicating the language learning journey.

In contrast to the preceding observations, a heightened level of proficiency in one's native language can serve as a double-edged sword when it comes to the acquisition of a foreign language among adult learners. This stems from the juxtaposition of their imperative need to articulate intricate thoughts and the accumulation of extensive life experiences, which can inadvertently impede their proficiency in using a foreign language, consequently resulting in a multitude of errors. Paradoxically, empirical evidence attests to the notion that linguistic experience in mastering one foreign language can positively influence the efficacy of acquiring subsequent foreign languages.

Motivation assumes a pivotal role in the realm of adult learning, acting as the propellant that not only triggers an individual into action but also harnesses their internal reservoir of resources, channeling their endeavors and actions in a directed manner.

When dealing with an adult audience, it becomes imperative to tailor the instructional approach to the unique individual characteristics of each student, carefully taking into account their societal roles. Establishing a conducive environment that fosters enhanced communicative

participation among students necessitates a commitment to cultivating a milieu of genuine, unstructured interaction characterized by responsiveness, active engagement, and an unwavering focus on the interlocutor. This interactive paradigm should be infused with a sense of curiosity and an attentive disposition.

Furthermore, fostering interpersonal harmony among students warrants not just the evaluation of language proficiency levels but also the consideration of the age demographic within the group. This aspect proves paramount in gauging student progress, rectifying errors, and commending accomplishments and exertions.

As articulated by A.V. Ballastov and other researchers [2], a set of paramount pedagogical prerequisites can be discerned for the efficacious instruction of a foreign language to adult learners. The salient characteristics inherent to adult learners encompass the following facets:

1. Adult learners manifest themselves as autonomous, self-regulating entities endowed with a reservoir of life experiences, including past educational undertakings.
2. Each adult learner harbors their own distinctive motivation for mastering a foreign language, often intricately intertwined with their professional aspirations.
3. Adult learners are inherently driven to directly apply theoretical knowledge in their daily lives and professional vocations.
4. Discerning in their pursuit of excellence, adult learners maintain high expectations with regard to the quality of instruction and the assessment of their performance outcomes.

In light of the aforementioned tenets, a set of foundational pedagogical principles in the realm of instructing adult audiences materializes, encompassing the following imperatives: individualization, capitalizing on antecedent life experiences, fostering collaborative activities, accentuating the pragmatic applicability of the educational content, explicating the teacher's role in orchestrating the educational process, delivering comprehensive consultations, and dispensing high-quality information.

Furthermore, an array of distinctive features, identified by numerous psychologists, underscores the pivotal facets pertinent to the pedagogy of adult learners:

1. The intrinsic motivation of adult learners stands as a linchpin, wherein the efficacy of their educational endeavors hinges upon their innate aspiration to acquire fresh skills and knowledge. While motivation cannot be imposed, it can be galvanized.
2. Adult learners selectively gravitate toward subjects they deem pertinent and indispensable to their practical existence.
3. The optimal learning mode for adult learners pivots upon the application of newfound knowledge into real-life situations, coupled with a regimen of regular review and reinforcement.
4. When instructing adults, the infusion of realistic scenarios sourced from authentic life experiences and the elucidation of concrete solutions prove pivotal.
5. The antecedent life experiences of adult learners wield a profound influence over their assimilation of novel knowledge.
6. The creation of an informal learning milieu stands as a prerogative, stemming from the fact that many adult learners may harbor unfavorable recollections associated with conventional educational settings.

7. The pedagogy for adult audiences necessitates the deployment of a diverse repertoire of teaching methods, incorporating the stimulation of multiple senses such as vision and

audition. Employing audio recordings, visual aids, and video clips can substantially enhance the learning experience. Engaging in discussions and dialogues also proves instrumental in cementing acquired knowledge.

8. Adult learners are best navigated and supported rather than subjected to scrutiny. A considerable number among them harbor self-critique, thus rendering competition potentially injurious due to apprehensions regarding public judgment.

The panorama of interpersonal interactions assumes an indispensable role in the effective tutelage of a foreign language to adult learners. Adhering to the psychological nuances of student interaction can optimize the pedagogical process and conduce to the attainment of superior results in adult education.

In my perspective, to ensure the effective instruction of a foreign language to adult learners, sustained and comprehensive interaction between the student and the teacher is indispensable at every phase of the educational process, spanning from the initial planning stages to the subsequent assessment of outcomes. G.A. Kitaygorodskaya underscores the significance of cultivating learning situations that stimulate students to unlock their creative potential, marshal their cognitive resources, and infuse their memory with emotional resonance, thereby enhancing the overall educational experience. For adult learners, the immediate and practical application of freshly acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies assumes a pivotal role, thus rendering the utilization of role-playing exercises and lifelike simulations notably efficacious.

Furthermore, it is imperative to acknowledge that adult learners exhibit heightened levels of intrinsic motivation. Consequently, it is of paramount importance to nurture and channel this motivation toward the attainment of predefined educational objectives. To facilitate the more effective retention of newly acquired vocabulary, I propose the integration of visual imagery and mnemonic associations. Moreover, in lieu of conventional grading methods, educators may encourage students to engage in self-assessment, thereby enabling a more accurate evaluation of their own progress, which can subsequently be discussed with the teacher.

The afore-discussed "competency-based" approach, oriented toward the cultivation of diverse skill sets, the shaping of opinions and attitudes, and the cultivation of a penchant for personal development, distinctly aligns with the expectations and aspirations of an adult audience in the realm of foreign language education.

REFERENCES

1. Nemov, R. S. (2003). *Psychology: A textbook for students of higher pedagogical educational institutions* (4th ed.). Humanitarian Publishing Center VLADOS.
2. Ballastov, A. V. (2012). Practical application of information technology in teaching adults professionally oriented foreign language communication in non-linguistic universities. *Vestnik TPGU*, (4), 74–79.
3. Kozlova, O. V. (2005). Integrative technology for teaching adults a foreign language. *Modern High-Tech Technologies*, (8), 135–137.
4. Kitaygorodskaya, G. A. (1978). *Optimal organization of the educational process in intensive adult foreign language learning. Psychology and Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages*. Moscow.